

ECONOMY

PERSPECTIVES OF RISK MINIMIZATION IN SMALL BUSINESS OF GEORGIA

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Abstract

Small business is developing dynamically in Georgia and faces many dangers of risk realization.

Liquidity risks of assets are relevant in small business, which can be defeated by implementing innovations and achieving rapid pace of technological development in this segment.

Small business of Georgia significantly depends on import. This situation should be changed through the growth of exported goods, in future.

It is important to gain the reputation of a reliable partner, for success of a small business, so minimizing reputational risks is the most important task of management.

The risk of competition is especially sensitive for small enterprises, because not only small enterprises, but also large market participants are often in competition with them.

Small business enterprises rarely apply for risk insurance in Georgia, which can be used to compensate losses.

It is necessary to create a clear vision of risk management, select and use the right risk managing strategy, for the stable development of small business.

Keywords: small business, risks, asset liquidity, inflation, risk minimization, import, insurance.

Small business is one of the most dynamically growing segment of the economy in Georgia. This is due to the fact that it does not require large human, material and financial resources for development, and is much more flexible and mobile compared to large businesses, and much more convenient and accessible for innovation and investment.

The European integration process faced small businesses in front of a new challenges in Georgia. These challenges are related to the problems of minimizing the risks of integration and globalization.

The involvement of small businesses of Georgia in the process of European integration creates new threats and at the same time strengthens probability of increasing the traditionally existing risks.

In recent years, small and medium-sized businesses have been developing dynamically in Georgia, and their share in economic development is increasing too. According to the data of the National Statistics Service of Georgia the share of small and medium-sized businesses in total turnover was 34.5% in 2022, while in 2015 it was only 18.1%. The main capital structure of small and medium-sized enterprises has changed, in the same period, if its share in the overall structure of the country's production potential was only 13.2% in 2015, in 2022 it was increased to 47.8%. This was caused by the fact that small business has become financially interesting for investments and the use of financial assets invested in this sphere is much more efficient.

Small and medium-sized businesses actively participate in solving the problem of unemployment in the

country, if small and medium-sized businesses employed only 43.1% of the total employees in 2015, this figure was 60.1% in 2022.

Small businesses face many danger of risk realization in Georgia during their activity process, which belongs to the groups of speculative or pure risks due to their internal nature.

Liquidity risks of assets have become the "Achilles heel" of this activity in small businesses, due to the growing dynamics of inflation processes, which can be defeated by implementing innovations and achieving rapid pace of technological development in this segment of economy. Due to the geopolitical situation of Georgia, liquidity risks in small business are also significantly related to external factors, namely: the problem of territorial integrity, ongoing military conflicts in Georgia's neighboring countries, changes in the country's legislation, economic crises, unfair competition, inflation, currency devaluation, and others. Internal liquidity risks of small enterprises are mainly related to faulty management, wrong monetary credit policy and wrong business strategy and tactics in Georgia.

Traditionally, one of the most sensitive risks in small business enterprises is the increase of cost of resources, due to the scarcity of financial resources. The magnitude and frequency of these risks are determined by the increase of prices on natural, energy and human resources, in domestic and foreign markets.

Small businesses significantly depend on imports and the cost of imported materials and semi-finished products in Georgia, like the whole country. From January to November of 2023 turnover of foreign trade with goods (without undeclared trade) amounted 19,612.8 million US dollars in Georgia, in which export

amounted 5,584.3 million US dollars, and import to 14,028.5 million US dollars. Negative trade balance of Georgia from January to November of 2023 amounted 8,444.2 million US dollars, which is 43.1 percent of foreign trade turnover.

We think that in future this undesirable situation should be changed due to growth of exported goods, like in small businesses, also in whole country, following the economic development of Georgia.

The danger of realization of technological risks is also high, in small businesses, since there are many difficulties associated with the introduction of innovations and the technological perfection. Nowadays, significant investments are being made with the help of startups and various governmental and non-governmental programs, in this segment of economy in Georgia.

The European Union supports the development of small and medium-sized businesses in Georgia. Through the EU4Business program, up to 50 different projects were operating in the country at different times, which total budget exceeded 320 million euros. The European Union is the largest donor and supporter of private sector development in Georgia. These efforts have already brought significant results – in 2019, more than 36,000 small and medium-sized businesses were supported in Georgia, as a result 30,000 new jobs and up to 400 million euros of additional income was created.

It is important to gain the reputation of a reliable partner, for success of a small business, so minimizing reputational risks is the most important task of management.

The risk of competition is especially sensitive for small enterprises, because of not only small enterprises, but also large market participants are often in competition with them.

First of all, small businesses should minimize such financial risks which are related to the growth of costs, violation of contractual conditions, taking immature and unsubstantiated financial obligations, providing low-quality products and services to customers, reputational damage, and etc. due to limited financial opportunities. This is possible only when the strategy and tactics of risk management in small business are consistent with the business environment and the changes that are related to the development of this enterprise.

In order to neutralize financial risks in small enterprise, it is necessary to develop measures that completely exclude high-risk financial transactions with suppliers and customers who systematically violate contractual obligations and other agreements. Also, those small enterprises who want to have a modern level of financial management should create risk concentration limits, which should include those financial operations that belong to the critical level of risks. That is often impossible in small enterprises, but if it is possible, an effective mechanism for minimizing risks will be their diversification, which implies a rational redistribution of expected risks.

Unfortunately, in order to save financial resources, small business enterprises rarely use risk insurance in

Georgia. However, insurance is an effective risk managing mechanism, which provides material compensation of losses. Small entrepreneur will protect his property, health of his employees by insurance, also will be protected from the costs caused by damaging other people's property and health due to his fault.

In order to maintain a stable development, it is necessary to create a clear vision of risk management in a small business enterprise. The formation of such visions is complicated by the multitude of operational problems in these enterprises, and it is impossible to create a risk management service or hire a qualified risk manager due to the lack of financial resources.

According to the law of Georgia "about competition", the competition agency must identify the facts of restriction of competition and unfair competition and protect small and medium-sized enterprises from the dictates of big business, by detecting "cartel" agreements against small and medium-sized businesses, limiting them and protecting the interests of consumers. This institution should become one of the important institutions for strengthening antimonopoly activities in the country, in future.

The development of small and medium-sized businesses is significantly prevented in the modern world by the danger of merging and absorbing small business objects by large businesses, which is motivated by the desire of corporations to grow, accumulate capital and reorganize. In such a case, the shareholders mainly focus on the growth of the shareholder's capital and using the mechanisms favorable to them, they try to carry out a specific action of merger or absorption in order to increase their own assets and opportunities on the markets.

The strategy of risk management in small business and the effectiveness of this strategy should be evaluated from three main positions, which are: the impact of shareholders' investment portfolios on common risks, the sensitivity to risks of the business environment, and the condition of liquidity of assets in case of realization of existing risks.

Innovative entrepreneurs do not run away from difficulties in Georgia and, they do not lose their professional interest in developing their business due to the difficulties created in business. As for the encouragement and financing of innovative activities by the government, we think that it is necessary to increase the volume of financing startup programs, increase the targeting and more support and promotion of innovative ideas by the government.

The European experience and practice of attracting venture investments in small and medium-sized businesses is still less used in Georgia, but venture capital is the resource that should give a push to the production of innovative products in this field and the integration of this business segment with the EU markets.

There is opinion in business circles in Georgia that in order to minimize risks in small business, it is necessary to create a special program. Purpose of this program will be the prevention of risks in small business. We believe that the existence of such a program will cause over-administration the activities of small businesses and restrict their freedom. Small enterprises

should be able to maintain a balance in risk management, naturally maintain the ability to be creative, overcome the difficulties and contradictions associated with risk management in small enterprises by their own efforts.

At the same time, we think that it is necessary that business associations systematically conduct seminars and trainings for small businesses on issues related to risk management, because the knowledge of risk management is an advantage that will definitely be manifested in the possibility of minimizing risks.

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